

MATERNAL, INFANT AND YOUNG CHILD NUTRITION INTERVENTIONS IMPLEMENTED IN FIFTY HEALTH CARE CENTERS IN FIVE LGAS OF BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *It is important to integrate Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition (MIYCN) related interventions to improve and help strengthen nutrition services at the healthcare system. The objective of this study is to identify the types of MIYCN interventions implemented at the health facilities, highlighting the different types of interventions that should be implemented and recommend ways to improve the implementation of these interventions at the Health Care Centers. It was a cross sectional study with a total of 200 Health care workers sampled in fifty (50) health care centres in five selected LGAs of Bayelsa State, which was selected purposively. A structured interviewer-administered questionnaire was administered to obtain the respondents information on the Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition interventions implemented at the various health facilities. In this study, the data entry were done with pie charts, Bar charts and Histograms to represent the frequency of nutrition intervention implemented in the health facilities, nutrition program implementation, special clinic and outreach days in the health facilities. Also, information on MIYCN Training and Implementation status were also presented, the challenges faced in MIYCN implementation and recommendations for Improvement were also reported by the healthcare workers. The*

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study help to create awareness on the recommended various MIYCN interventions that should be implemented at the Health care system to improve maternal, infant and young child nutrition interventions. It was also noted that MIYCN programmes are not given the necessary attention at the health facilities, and there were no designated clinic and outreach days for MIYCN interventions.

Introduction

Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition (MIYCN) is an important public health concern even globally. But to improve this public health concern, MIYCN interventions should be integrated into the health care system programmes to be implemented regularly, because, despite the global understanding of the importance of reducing maternal and child undernutrition, it still remains highly prevalent (Chou, Walker, & Kanyangarara, 2019). Maternal and child nutrition interventions can be delivered through the health care system which is considered the most effective platform to reach out to women and children in the first 1000 days of life, (Heidkamp, Wilson and Menon, 2020). Gaps in coverage and attention to quality MIYCN intervention implementations have hindered the improvement in the outcomes associated with the services. In 2016, the WHO issued new guidelines on antenatal care (ANC) for a positive pregnancy experience (WHO, 2016), but evidence-based interventions to improve maternal nutrition are currently poorly integrated in ANC services globally. The coverage of most MIYCN interventions falls far below the coverage of the health care services in the system through which they are being delivered, for

example the ANC, where the coverage of iron-folic acid (IFA) supplement consumption is about half of ANC visits, (Heidkamp, et.al., 2020). There are missed opportunities due to some factors like, no special clinic days for MIYCN activities, shortage of commodities, non-commitment of the health workers to MIYCN programmes because of no special remuneration attached to it. These low coverage suggests that there is the need to fully implement and deliver these services effectively. Closing these gaps can be achieved by integrating MIYCN programmes into the health care system, thereby increasing nutrition intervention coverage and services, these should be made an immediate priority. Nutrition care should be an integral part of healthcare delivery package in the health care centers, this is to ensure the prevention of diet and diet related health problems. It is important to integrate it, in order to help strengthen the nutrition services in the healthcare system to address some issues like nutrition counseling, breastfeeding, micronutrient supplementation, deworming, growth monitoring and promotion, nutrition interventions during pre and post natal periods, etc. The World Health Organization (2019a), highlighted that the relationship between Universal Health Coverage and nutrition cannot be achieved without ensuring

adequate access to quality nutrition services at the health care facilities, (World Health Organization, 2019a). Advancing Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition in Nigeria, should be focused on promoting adequate nutrition in pregnancy, during lactation, exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of a child's life, timely introduction of complementary foods and continued breastfeeding up to two years and beyond amongst others, and the implementation of some other nutrition specific and nutrition sensitive interventions.

Nutrition interventions should also include counselling and nutrition education on the promotion of healthy eating habits and supporting specific groups like the pregnant women, infants and children, (WHO and UNICEF, 2018). According to UNICEF, the healthcare system is planned to achieving the universal health coverage through which nutrition interventions are delivered to Mothers, Caregivers and Children, (UNICEF, 2019). Noting that, poor access to healthcare that have well integrated nutrition interventions can also mean that quality nutrition services will not reach the deserved population. The nature of nutrition interventions integrated into the healthcare system may vary in the different systems and may be due to the specific needs. For example, the healthcare systems in tailored to deal with stunting, wasting, micronutrient deficiencies and maternal nutrition, UNICEF, (2019).

Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition (MIYCN) and related interventions in the health care centers should focus on the implementation of all MIYCN interventions, ensure availability of the various commodities and services, health workers training, community engagement, address the factors influencing maternal and child feeding practices. There is also the need for 'good MIYCN service delivery' in all health centers, well monitored and evaluated across all units, with focus on equity, for mothers and children to achieve and retain their full health potential, Fenta, Endris and Mengistu, (2020).

The need to improve in maternal, infant and young child nutrition interventions in the health care centres is essential to promote good health, enhance the overall health outcomes and reduce maternal and child mortality. Lack of maternal, infant and young child nutrition interventions during pregnancy and childhood can lead to low birth weight, wasting, underweight, stunting and other nutritional problems and strengthening nutrition interventions, help to address these critical needs.

The aim of this study is to identify the types of MIYCN interventions implemented at the health facilities, highlighting the different types of Maternal Infant and Young Child Nutrition interventions that should be implemented and recommend ways to improve the implementation of these interventions at the Health Care Centers in Bayelsa State

Literature Review

In 2022, globally, about 149 million children under 5 were estimated to be stunted, that is too short for their age, 45 million were estimated to be wasted, that is too thin for their height and 37 million were overweight or obese, nearly half of deaths among children under 5 years of age are linked to undernutrition, (WHO, 2024). The report of World Health Organization, (2023) on the Comprehensive implementation plan on maternal, infant and young child nutrition, biennial report, by the Director-General describes the progress made in realizing the six target actions on the implementation plan on maternal, infant and young child nutrition, (World Health Organization, 2023).

The report provides information on the status of national measures on the following plans:

Stunting – It is stated that childhood stunting reduced at the rate of 1.7% yearly from 26.3% in 2012 to 22.3% in 2022. If the improvement continues to 2025, there would be improvement in the number of stunted children with a projected excess of 31.5 million stunted children by 2025, compared to the target of 107 million. Only the European and Western Pacific regions are projected to reach the target of a 40% reduction in the number of stunted children by 2025 from the 2012 baseline. From the 153 countries where progress assessments are possible, 62 countries are on track to reach the 2025 target, (WHO, 2023).

Anaemia – According to World Health Organization (2023), the global prevalence of anaemia in women of child bearing age from

2012 to 2019 increased from 28.5% to 29.9%, missing the global target of a 50% and reduction compared to the 2012 baseline. Reduced progress is noticed across all regions in the countries. In 2019, the South-East Asia Region accounted for 42.8% cases of anaemia in women of reproductive age and the African Region for 18.5%, (WHO, 2023).

Low birth weight – Prevalence of low birth weight in newborns reduced from 15.0% in 2012 to 14.7% in 2020, missing the global target of 30% reduction compared to the 2012 baseline. In 2020, the South-East Asia and African regions recorded half of all babies born with low birth weight with 39.8% and 26.8% cases, respectively, (WHO, 2023).

Overweight – There is global increase in the prevalence of childhood overweight, from 5.5% in 2012 to 5.6% in 2022 and is projected to remain at 5.6% in 2025, almost achieving the global target of no increase. Americas Region observed an increase from 7.8% in 2012 to 8.5% in 2022 and an increase in the in the Western Pacific Region from 6.3% in 2012 to 8.1% in 2022. The European Region observed a decrease from 9.3% in 2012 to 7.1% in 2022, (WHO, 2023).

Exclusive breastfeeding – About 47.7% of all infants under the age of 6 months in 2021 were exclusively breastfed, an increase from the 2012 baseline of 37.0%. In 2025, 53.4% of infants less than 6 months are projected to be exclusively breastfed, exceeding the 2025 target by increasing the rate to 50%, (WHO, 2023).

Wasting – Childhood wasting decreased from 2012 of 7.5% to 6.8% in 2022. It is projected that in 2025, 6.6% of all children under 5 years will be wasted, missing the global target of less than 5%. It was observed that half of all wasted children live in the South-East Asia Region (53.8%), followed by the African Region (22.3%) and Eastern Mediterranean Region (13.9%), (WHO, 2023).

The four global targets of – anaemia, wasting, stunting and overweight – are embedded into the Sustainable Development Goals framework to track progress. It was published in 2018 by WHO and UNICEF discussion paper providing on the targets that the goals could be reached in 2030, (WHO/UNICEF, 2019).

- A reduction of 50% in the number of children under 5 years of age who are stunted
- A reduction of 50% of anaemia in women of reproductive age
- A 30% reduction in low birth weight
- Reduce and maintain childhood overweight to less than 3%
- Increase the rate of exclusive breastfeeding in the first 6 months up to 70% or more
- Reduce and maintain childhood wasting to less than 3%.

Methodology

Area of Study

This study was carried out in 50 Health Care Centers in five Local Government Areas of Bayelsa State. The LGAs are Kolokuma,

Opokuma, Nembe, Ogbia, Sagbama, and Yenagoa LGAs of Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Population of the Study:

A total of 200 Health care workers were sampled in the 50 health care centers.

Study Design

It was a cross sectional study, aimed at studying the Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition Interventions implemented in the fifty health care centers in five LGAs of Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Sample Selection

A three-stage sampling technique was used to select the LGAs, the Health Care Centers and the health workers for the study these were selected purposively.

Stage 1: Selection of the Local Government Area: The selected LGAs were

- Kolokuma Opokuma LGA is made up of eleven wards and eleven health facilities
- Nembe LGA is made up of 13 ward and 28 health facilities
- Ogbia LGA is made up of 13 ward and 26 health facilities
- Sagbama LGA is made up of 14 ward and 30 health facilities
- Yenagoa LGAs is made up of 15 ward and 36 health facilities. They were identified and selected purposively by using a descriptive cross-sectional concept.

Stage 2: Selection of ten health facilities from each LGA were selected.

Stage 3: In the third stage, four health workers each were selected from each health facility, giving a total of 200 health workers,

Recruitment and training of research assistants

Officers were recruited and trained as research assistants on the methods of the questionnaire administration. The training was on the procedure for the distribution and filling of the questionnaire.

Data collection and processing

A structured interviewer-administered questionnaire were administered which was used to obtain the respondents information on the Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition interventions implemented at the various health facilities

Data Analysis

In this study, the data entry were done with Pie chart, Bar charts and Histograms to represent the status of the healthcare care centers, frequency of nutrition intervention messages implemented in the health facilities, health facility type, nutrition program implementation, special clinic and outreach days in the health facilities. The MIYCN Training and Implementation status were also presented, while the challenges in MIYCN Implementation and recommendations for Improvement were also reported by the healthcare workers.

Result

Figure 1: Status of the Healthcare Center (n50)

Figure 1a Facility Type

- Most **72%** of the facilities are Primary Health care Centers, while **28%** are Comprehensive Health care centers.

Fig. 1a: Health facility type distribution

Figure 1b

- All health centers (100%) implement **Vitamin A Supplementation.**

- High coverage is also seen in **Growth Monitoring (84%)** and **Deworming (64%)**.

- Major gaps: **No facility implements food demonstration, monitoring and evaluation** of nutrition interventions.

Though, intervention like Vitamin A is widespread, management of Acute Malnutrition

with Ready-to-Use-Therapeutic Foods are lacking, while, practical (like food demonstration) and Evaluation process (monitoring and evaluation) components are absent - indicating gap in hands-on nutrition activities.

Fig. 1b: Nutrition program implementation

Figure 2: Frequency of Nutrition intervention messages implemented in the Health facilities (n50)

- **Growth Monitoring** stands out with **90% implementation**.

- Most other interventions like **Vitamin A, Deworming** and **Breastfeeding Counseling** are delivered **occasionally (64–82%)**.

- **Food Demonstrations** are completely absent (**100% not done**).

Fig. 2: Frequency of Nutrition Intervention Messages.

Figure 3: Frequency of other health interventions messages implemented in the Health facilities (n50)

• **Immunization** messages are delivered on every clinic day in 100% of facilities – a standout performer.

- **Family Planning** and **HIV Counseling & Testing** show moderate delivery but still include **monthly** and **occasional** frequencies.
- **Malaria Prevention** and **WASH** are largely **occasional** or **not done**, indicating low coverage.

Fig. 3: Frequency of Other Health Messages.

Figure 4: Special Clinic and Outreach Days in the Health facilities (n50)

- None, **0%** of facilities have dedicated MIYCN clinic or outreach days.
- In contrast, **100%** have immunization clinic and outreach days.

Fig. 4: Special clinic and outreach days

Figure 5: MIYCN Training and Implementation

- Only **41%** of the 200 health workers had received training on MIYCN.
- Of those trained:**
 - Only, **20%** focus exclusively on nutrition interventions.

- MIYCN activities are **combined with other services**, potentially diluting their impact.

The lack of dedicated time or space for MIYCN interventions undermines their visibility and effectiveness within routine service delivery

- About, **18%** combine nutrition with other health tasks.

- While, **3%** are diverted to unrelated activities.

Even among trained staff, many are not fully dedicated to MIYCN tasks, limiting program fidelity.

Fig 5: MIYCN training and implementation

Figure 6: Challenges in MIYCN Implementation

Most frequent challenges:

- Financial constraints (76%)
- Manpower shortage (72%)
- Health worker absenteeism (64%)

- **Other notable issues include:** Lack of logistics, socio-cultural barriers and poor attention to MIYCN activities. Structural and systemic constraints are the major barriers, not just knowledge or willingness.

Fig 6: Challenges in MIYCN Implementation

Figure 7: Recommendations for the Improvement of MIYCN programmes in the Health Care Centers

Universally supported solutions:

- Recruitment and training of more health workers on MIYCN (100%)
- Caregiver counselling to help change their behaviour (100%)
- Stipends for MIYCN intervention workers, to help encourage them, just like other health programmes (100%)

- Most, **90%** support for special MIYCN clinic days.

- While, **84%** prefer trained officers to focus solely on nutrition interventions.

There is strong consensus on what is needed: Dedicated staff, better funding and structural support.

Fig 7: Recommendations for Improvement

Discussion

Status of the Healthcare Centers

The study shows that 28% of the 50 Health care centers sampled were Comprehensive Health centers. Comprehensive Health Centers (CHCs), are healthcare facilities that offer a wider range of services to meet the needs of a population, which includes advanced preventative health

care. They are aimed to serve as a primary point of contact for health care seeking services within a specific geographic area and serves as a referral center for the Primary Health Care Centres, they are to address patient's overall health needs (Labonte, Pooyak, & Baum, 2013). They provide a wide range of comprehensive care to the primary healthcare and make referrals to the secondary health care facilities, (Labonte , et.al.,

2013). Primary healthcare center is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), (2024) as a health care center that prioritizes people's needs, an essential health care that is accessible, affordable and practical for all and these includes health promotion and disease prevention, (WHO, 2024), in this study 72% of the sampled health facilities were Primary Health centers and all the 50 (100%) health care centers implement Vitamin A Supplementation activities (VAS) in the health facilities regularly. In 2013, the World Health Organization, classified vitamin A deficiency as a public health problem, which affects about one in three children aged 6 to 59 months, with the highest rates in sub-Saharan Africa and South-East Asia, (Imdad, Yakoob and Sudfeld, 2011). Due to this, WHO recommends the six monthly delivery of one dose of Vitamin A Capsule of 100,000 IU to infants 6–11 months and 200,000 IU of Vitamin A capsules to children aged 12 to 59 months, (WHO, 2011).

To reduce the burden of worm infestation in children aged 12 to 59 months, WHO recommends that children of that age be dewormed twice a year, with 200 mg of albendazole tablets, this is aimed at the reduction of the intensity of the worm infections, which is associated with poor health outcomes, (WHO, 2012). In this study deworming exercise is implemented in 64% of the health facilities. Growth monitoring and promotion (GMP) activities should be focused on tracking the child's growth and development, through regular measurements of their weight, height and length,

which is then plotted on the growth chart. This process helps to assess if the child is growing well and identifies potential growth faltering and other health and nutritional problems, 84% of the facilities in this study implements growth monitoring of children regularly. Conducted research by (Leroy, Brander and Frongillo, 2025), raises important questions about the current practice of GMP, which is widely implemented in low and middle-income countries. The management of acute malnutrition is a decentralised approach in which the management of the children is shifted from facility-based to community-based treatment from the primary health care centres, (WHO, WFP, UNICEF and UNSCN, 2007). This approach have been used by many government and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in the management of severe acute malnourished children, (World Vision, 2012). Only 4% of the facilities implements management of Severe Acute Malnutrition with Ready-to-Use-Therapeutic Foods in this study, no food demonstration, no monitoring and evaluation of nutrition activities is being carried out. Food demonstration activities at the health facilities for mothers and caregivers is a valuable tool to improve their nutrition knowledge and practices. Food demonstrations is always focused on preparing adequate nutritious meals using locally available foods, also, encouraging breastfeeding, adequate and timely complementary feeding and understanding appropriate feeding practices for mothers and

children, (Vaillancourt et.al., 2019). Effective food demonstrations help convey clear messages about nutrition and health, which includes the mothers and caregivers cooking skills, access to nutritious food and budget planning.

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) activities at the health facilities is the process of tracking and assessing the implementation of health programs and interventions to improve service delivery and achieve desired outcomes. Regular collection, analyses and using of data to identify the strengths and weaknesses of programme, make informed decisions and demonstrate impact of health programs, (Braithwaite, McKenzie and Pruitt, 2013). Unless monitoring and evaluation activities are done at the health care centres to evaluate MIYCN programmes, the whole process will be a waste of time and money. According to Braithwaite, et.al., (2013), in the study on 'Community-based participatory evaluation: The healthy start approach, Health Promotion Practices', a well-planned monitoring and evaluation can even be done by the health team and the community together. The team need to be taught some necessary skills and with a good monitoring system in place, (Braithwaite, et.al., 2013).

Food demonstration is a unique and effective way to give mothers and caregivers good and basic nutrition information and skills in the health care centres and at the community level which can improve confidence in the kitchen, in their cooking skills and the promotion of

healthier food choices in the diet, (Henderson, 2022). Learning food demonstration skills in a community setting is necessary, (Hashimi, Boggs and Harada, 2020).

Frequency of Nutrition intervention messages implemented in the Health facilities

Implementing MIYCN activities regularly at the health care centres help to improve goals and targets, expected for maternal, infant and young child nutrition interventions, several MIYCN frameworks and initiatives have emerged in recent years, these initiatives can only be effective if regular and timely supply and implementations are carried out, (Bhutta, Das and Rizvi, 2013). An actionable regular data is essential to address the issue of malnutrition and the required multisectoral response having data from multiple levels. Data that capture relevant information on MIYCN activities are key. According to Requejo, Newby and Bryce, (2013), information on the coverage of nutrition programmes, access to these programmes and nutrition outcomes across different population groups is important. But in this study, 70% of the facilities, deliver most MIYCN messages occasionally while other interventions like immunization are implemented weekly and regularly.

Frequency of other health intervention messages implemented in the Health facilities

The Lancet Maternal and Child Nutrition Series, (Bhutta, et.al., 2013), recommended that if

nutrition interventions be scaled up to 90%, could reduce stunting by 20%, reduce infant and child mortality by 15%. Also, routine monitoring of nutrition intervention coverages enables rapid assessment of progress and helps identify any need for corrections and improvement. Hence, monitoring the scale and quality of MIYCN interventions which is now incorporated into most national policies and programs, is essential for tracking country progress towards national and global goals, (World Health Organization Global nutrition policy review, 2018). In this study, programmes like immunization family planning and HIV testing and counselling messages are delivered weekly and regularly and with special clinic days.

Special Clinic Days in the Health facilities

The study shows that none of the health facility have any special clinic day for MIYCN activities, all (100%) of the health facilities have weekly clinic days and outreaches for immunization activities, 36% have regular special clinic days Family Planning activities, while all the facilities combine MIYCN activities with other health facility activities to implement occasionally, showing non commitment to MIYCN programmes. All the facilities conduct immunization sessions/outreach programmes regularly, while there is no MIYCN outreach programmes in all the facilities. There are no special clinic days for MIYCN activities, while programmes like immunization, family planning, HIV Counselling and testing all have special clinic days. It is good to note that the

health care system is responsible to play essential role in the delivery of nutrition-specific interventions, especially those targeted at the well-being of mothers and children (World Health Organization, 2019b). The 2013 Lancet series on nutrition highlighted ten (10) nutrition-specific interventions that, if scaled up, could significantly reduce child mortality associated with undernutrition, these include folic acid supplementation during pregnancy, multiple micronutrient supplementation during pregnancy and breastfeeding, calcium supplementation during pregnancy, exclusive breastfeeding for six months then appropriate and timely complementary feeding practices from 6 months of age, Vitamin A Supplementation (6–59 months), management of severe acute malnutrition (SAM), management of moderate acute malnutrition (MAM) with nutrition education and food demonstration, (Bhutta et al., 2013). All of these nutrition-specific interventions are delivered through the health care system to address undernutrition issues in mothers and children, with evidence for the effectiveness of the impact of MIYCN interventions, (Pérez-Escamilla and Engmann, 2019).

Health workers MIYCN Training information

Evidence-based maternal, infant and young child nutrition (MIYCN) training and counselling is an essential strategy for promoting and optimizing maternal, infant and young child programmes, (United Nations, 2015). The

effectiveness of MIYCN counselling should be based on quality training and counselling skills of trained health workers, which can make the difference in the lives of mothers and children and in the programme. Training health care providers on MIYCN will help to improve the outcomes in feeding frequencies, energy intake, supplementations, dietary variety and nutrition education for mothers and children, (Mallan and Miller, 2019). In this study, 200 (100%) of health workers were sampled and 41% have been trained on MIYCN, 20% of the trained officers' implements only MIYCN interventions, 20% implement MIYCN in addition to other health care programmes, the health workers are over utilized, while 3% of the trained officers are assigned to implements other health activities instead of MIYCN interventions. There should be policies to prioritize MIYCN trained health officers to oversee the MIYCN activities and be committed to the programme, this will help to improve the outcome, while lack of priority setting, health staff over-utilization, limited sustained funding for trainings pose challenges to effective nutrition training for health care providers, (Kouam, Delisle and Ebbing, 2014). Subsequently, if the MIYCN trained health officers do not concentrate to implement the activity at the health care facilities, it will inhibit effective knowledge transfer to mothers and caregivers, while non-commitment of the implementation of MIYCN activities, will challenge the programme, (Nguyen, Kim and Billah, 2016).

Challenges to the implementation of Nutrition interventions in the health facilities

The study shows that 46% of the facilities complained of lack of commodities most of the time, 34% complained of socio-cultural beliefs and practices and 76% complained of financial challenges. Health workers absenteeism from work is 64%, 72% complained of shortage of manpower, while 36% complained of no special attention to MIYCN activities. For effective implementation and scale up of MIYCN at the health care centres, it is important to provide health workers and frontline workers with commodities and Social and Behavioural Change (SBC) materials to improve counselling skills and shifting the mothers and caregivers norms towards MIYCN. Delivery of MIYCN messages and interventions are embedded in the UNICEF's IYCF counselling messages and cards, (UNICEF, 2012). The study of Albury, Hall and Syed, (2019) on "Communication practices for delivering health behaviour change conversations in primary health care: A systematic review and thematic synthesis points to the importance of training health workers and frontline workers to deliver nutrition interventions at the health care centres to mother and child". This finding aligns with evidence that interpersonal communication in primary health care work is best when building on patient-initiated discussions, (Albury et al., 2019).

The study of Chowdhury, Khan and Rashid, (2022), on the “Prevalence and correlates of severe under-5 child anthropometric failure measured by the composite index of severe anthropometric failure in Bangladesh”, found that there were gaps in the anthropometric measurement of infants and young children. Although, it was observed that some children were weighed without the measurement of their height, which meant that the anthropometric measurement was not adequately used for the assessment of their growth, (Chowdhury, Khan and Rashid, 2022). According to Warren, Frongillo and Rawat, (2020) in the study on ‘Building implementation science in nutrition’ stated that in the future, nutrition needs to explore new options for innovative finance, this can be achieved from lessons learned from other development sectors, like education and health sectors to improve nutrition programmes, (Warren et al., 2020).

Recommendations for the Improvement of MIYCN programmes in the Health Care Centers

Lack of training and retraining of health workers in the health centres will create gaps and missed opportunities in MIYCN intervention programmes, in the study on “Quality of nutrition services in primary health care facilities: implications for integrating nutrition into the health system in Bangladesh” by Billah, Saha and Khan, (2017), stated some missed opportunities in growth monitoring and promotion which is intended to create an

opportunity for interaction between healthcare workers and mothers regarding health and wellbeing of their children. There were also gaps in the counselling of pregnant mothers on diets during pregnancy and breastfeeding, this shows that mothers were not receiving enough nutrition information from health care services, (Chowdhury, Khan and Rashid, 2022). Studies have also shown that good quality nutrition counselling was effective in changing infant and child feeding practices (Nguyen, Pramanik and Billah, 2022). Therefore, it is important to invest in developing the skills of health workers and creating enabling environment for counselling in the health care facilities.

In this study, all the 50 health facilities sampled supported the recruitment and training of more health workers on MIYCN intervention, 80% supported the recruitment and training of volunteer workers to support the activities, all supported the counselling of mothers and caregivers. Most, 90% supported a designated special clinic days for MIYCN activities, 84% suggested that trained MIYCN officers should focus on the implementation of the activities, while all health workers need stipends to support the trained MIYCN Officers in the interventions, just like other health care programmes like immunization, family planning and HIV programmes. Regular and weekly special clinic days for MIYCN activities will enable caregivers to track changes in their nutrition care, it will create awareness on the importance of MIYCN interventions and its interpretations, optimum

participation contributes to early identification of nutrition problems and to provide solutions, (Nyavani, Xikombiso and Fhumudzani, 2016).

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study on Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition (MIYCN) interventions in healthcare centres highlighted the positive impact of MIYCN interventions on maternal and child nutrition. The study help to create awareness on the recommended various MIYCN interventions that should be implemented at the Health care system to improve maternal, infant and young child nutrition. It is also noted that maternal knowledge and understanding of nutrition interventions will help reduce morbidity and mortality related to malnutrition. Adherence to the regular commitment and implementation of MIYCN interventions will help improve the nutritional status of mothers and children aged 6 to 59 months. Nutrition education and counselling programmess within the healthcare settings will help improve maternal knowledge, attitudes and behaviours towards MIYCN. Integrating nutrition-focused social and behavioral change (SBC) and community-based programs into the healthcare system is crucial for comprehensive coverage and improved outcomes. To sustain these interventions, it is

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important to build the capacity of health care workers and community members on MIYCN to provide effective counselling and support. The study emphasizes the positive impact of MIYCN interventions in the healthcare settings and highlighting the improvement on the interventions and availability of commodities and manpower.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made from this study

- i. Health care centres interventions should include the focus on promoting MIYCN activities
- ii. There should be designated clinic days for MIYCN activities in health care centres
- iii. More health care workers should be trained on MIYCN
- iv. Health workers trained on MIYCN should be allowed to oversee the interventions
- v. There should be regular monitoring and evaluation of MIYCN activities
- vi. There should be improvement in data reporting of MIYCN interventions

Limitations experienced in the study

- a. Not being able to select the health care facilities at the hard-to-reach communities because of high cost of transportation and security reasons
- b. Funding limitations
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